

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

dto-bioflow.eu

USE CASES

From Data to Decisions: DTO-BioFlow Use Cases

Delivering evidence-based knowledge to support marine biodiversity monitoring, restoration, and protection.

Funded by
the European Union

Acknowledgment

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From Insight to Impact

The Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) are at the heart of the DTO-BioFlow initiative, translating complex scientific capabilities into tangible digital solutions for marine biodiversity monitoring and management.

Designed to showcase the power of an **end-to-end digital approach**, these use cases connect cutting-edge biodiversity observations with AI-enhanced models, analytical tools, and the infrastructure of the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

Each DUC serves as a living example of how real-world marine challenges can be addressed through integrated digital workflows. They all address a pressing challenge for ocean sustainability and propose an integrated, evidence-based solution.

Marine Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) Management

Marine Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) are a major threat to marine ecosystems and biodiversity across Europe. Early detection, forecasting, and rapid response are essential tools to prevent their spread. This DUC focuses on using genetic monitoring, citizen science, and environmental data to provide **early warnings and predictive models** for managing NIS in Europe's coastal regions.

Challenge

Invasive marine species often go undetected until it's too late.

Limited data and unclear response strategies often hinder effective action. Environmental agencies need **timely, evidence-based guidance** to detect, track, assess, and respond to biological invasions.

Solution

This DUC proposes an integrated approach to detect, predict and manage marine invasions.

The combined data sources help identify invasion hotspots, trace transmission pathways, and predict spreading vectors, providing timely, actionable insights to support faster and more targeted responses.

Data and monitoring networks used

Genetic observatories (EMO BON), citizen science, systematic monitoring, environmental data, and socio-economic data (from e.g. traffic, ports, marinas)

Bio-ORACLE

Expected Outputs

Biogeographic maps

Early warning alerts

Management recommendations

The use case also highlights essential Digital Twin capabilities.

- **Event anticipation:** Early detection and rapid response to NIS
- **Gap analysis:** Reveals missing data and analytical limitations within biodiversity monitoring flows

Useful for

- **Environmental agencies:** municipalities, county councils, port and marine authorities
- **Public bodies reporting** under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and implementing the Ballast Water Management Convention (BWMC)

Learn more on development and read the publications

Impact from Off-shore infrastructure

The expansion of offshore infrastructure (such as wind farms, energy cables, and subsea installations) introduces new pressures on marine biodiversity. This use case explores how these human-made structures affect species movement, connectivity, and behavior, especially for mobile species like fish and marine mammals. The goal is to support **adaptive planning** and **low-impact infrastructure development** by integrating biodiversity knowledge into the early stages of marine spatial planning

Challenge

Offshore infrastructure impacts on marine species are unknown and overlooked in planning.

Without reliable data on species presence, migration, and sensitivity, infrastructure projects risk disrupting key habitats and migration routes—**potentially undermining biodiversity targets.**

Solution

This DUC develops a spatial decision-support tool that combines biologging, acoustic, environmental, and human activity data

It models species movements and habitat use, using Lagrangian simulations to predict interactions with offshore infrastructure, **supporting smarter, biodiversity-aware planning.**

Data and monitoring networks used

Fish telemetry, marine mammal acoustic data, environmental layers, EMODnet, stock data, species distributions.

Expected Outputs

A decision support Platform

Optimised marine spatial planning

Data uncertainty assessment

The use case also highlights essential Digital Twin capabilities.

- **Response anticipation:** Predicts how marine species react to offshore infrastructure and activity
- **Spatial intelligence:** Supports biodiversity-informed planning through dynamic ecological modelling
- **Gap analysis:** Identifies missing data and model limitations in species distribution and movement

Useful for

- Marine spatial planners and regulators
- Energy developers and infrastructure operators
- Environmental agencies

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Assessing pelagic biodiversity and human impact

Plankton play a foundational role in ocean ecosystems and are highly sensitive to environmental change. This use case enhances biodiversity assessments by integrating traditional microscopy, automated imaging, and genetic methods **to better track plankton diversity** and **assess how it is affected by human pressures** such as climate change and pollution.

Challenge

Current plankton monitoring is limited in resolution and scope.

Traditional microscopy methods are time-consuming and often miss shifts in species composition, making it difficult to detect and interpret changes caused by human activities.

Solution

This DUC enhances biodiversity monitoring by integrating microscopy, imaging, and genetic data with environmental context.

The integration of these approaches provides a more complete picture of pelagic diversity and enables improved indicators to assess the effects of human pressures on marine ecosystems

Data and monitoring networks used

Imaging and genetic data, environmental data.

EMODnet
European Marine Observation and Data Network

OBIS
OCEAN BIODIVERSITY INFORMATION SYSTEM

LifeWatch
ERIC

Expected Outputs

Improved Plankton diversity indicators for MSFD and OSPAR reporting

Analytical insights on how human activities affect pelagic ecosystems and their functions

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated.

- **Data integration:** Merges novel biological and environmental data for ecosystem-scale assessments
- **Impact analysis:** Links human pressures to changes in plankton diversity and ecosystem function
- **Gap identification:** Highlights limitations in current pelagic monitoring and indicator systems

Useful for

- Marine monitoring agencies
- Environmental researchers and institutions

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Spatial planning of sustainable mariculture

Aquaculture is a rapidly expanding sector with high potential for sustainable food production, but it must be carefully managed to avoid environmental harm. This use case supports **data-driven spatial planning for mariculture** by integrating environmental, biological, and eDNA data to identify optimal farm sites, minimize ecological risks, and promote ecosystem-based aquaculture.

Challenge

Sustainable mariculture lacks reliable planning tools.

Uncertainty around site suitability, biomass yield, and species interactions limits the adoption of low-impact, multi-trophic systems and increases operational risk.

Solution

This DUC develops predictive tools for smarter site selection.

By combining monitoring data, remote sensing, and eDNA, it models species impacts, forecasts yield, and supports climate-resilient mariculture planning.

Data and monitoring networks used

Monitoring data, environmental data, eDNA data, Remote sensing products and climate projections.

Expected Outputs

Site-specific models

Predictive tools

Planning support for low-impact aquaculture development

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated

- **Scenario simulation:** Tests climate and management options for mariculture performance
- **Risk forecasting:** Anticipates harmful species effects at specific sites
- **Data integration:** Combines genomic, environmental, and observational data for planning

Useful for

- Aquaculture operators
- Marine spatial planners
- Regulatory agencies

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Ecosystem-Based Spatial Planning & MPA Management

Marine habitats provide vital ecosystem services—such as carbon sequestration, habitat buffering, and biodiversity support, but species-level traits underpinning these services remain largely unlinked to spatial planning and MPA design. This use case builds a **species-traits database** to map benthic biodiversity to ecosystem services, enabling more informed and ecosystem-based marine spatial planning.

Challenge

Current planning overlooks specific biological traits that underpin ecosystem services.

Without linking traits (e.g. filter feeding, burrowing) to functional outcomes, planners lack precise tools to evaluate how human activities impact service delivery.

Solution

This DUC creates a public species-traits database, connecting biological traits to ecosystem services via asset-service matrices.

Statistical models then assess how pressures like coastal development or fishing might alter service delivery, informing adaptive and sustainable MPA planning.

Data and monitoring networks used

Species distribution and habitat data, trait and functional data, spacial data, Human pressure layers.

EMODnet
European Marine Observation and Data Network

OBIS
OCEAN BIODIVERSITY INFORMATION SYSTEM

EMODnet

BIOLOGY

LifeWatch
ERIC

FishBase

MarLIN
Marine Biological Association

Expected Outputs

A species-trait database linked to ecosystem services

Trait-to-service models showing how pressures affect service delivery

Planning Tools to guide adaptive MPA and spatial planning decisions

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated

- **Functional mapping:** Links species traits to ecosystem services across space
- **Pressure response modelling:** Simulates how human activities alter service delivery
- **Knowledge integration:** Combines ecological, functional, and spatial data for planning support

Useful for

- Marine spatial planners
- Conservation managers
- Policy advisor

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Lower-Trophic Level Biomass Monitoring for Ocean Governance

Zooplankton such as Calanus species form a vital link in marine food webs and act as key indicators of ocean health. This use case builds a continuous **monitoring system to track plankton biomass** at high resolution using acoustic and optical sensors, supporting data-informed governance decisions like fishing quotas and marine traffic management.

Challenge

Traditional methods for monitoring plankton biomass are limited in scope and frequency.

Sparse patchy distributions and environmental variability mean plankton are poorly represented in governance datasets, hindering timely decision-making.

Solution

This DUC deploys acoustic echosounders and optical cameras on autonomous platforms to capture real-time plankton biomass.

Data-driven sensor fusion and particle tracking models provide continuous updates on biomass distribution, supporting responsive ocean governance and ecosystem understanding

Data and monitoring networks used

Ocean observations, Satellite imagery, oceanographic data, Optical sensors (SilCam).

Expected Outputs

Interactive maps

Decision dashboards for regulators

Ongoing publicly accessible data streams

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated

- **Event detection:** Real-time tracking of plankton blooms and mass events
- **Governance support:** Dashboards linking biomass trends to decision-making contexts
- **Gap identification:** Pinpoints spatial and temporal data shortages in plankton monitoring

Useful for

- Fishing regulators
- Port and maritime authorities
- Ocean governance bodies

Learn more on development and read the publications

Ecosystem Services Including Carbon Sequestration

The ocean plays a vital role in the global carbon cycle by capturing CO₂ through the biological carbon pump. This use case develops **a global 3D/4D carbon flux product** by integrating particle size and concentration data from UVP sensors with existing carbon export measurements, supporting policy, climate models, and governance of marine carbon removal approaches.

Challenge

Limited data makes ocean carbon flux difficult to quantify accurately.

Gaps in observations, such as particle size dynamics and fragmentation, limit accurate estimates of ocean carbon sequestration, hindering climate modelling and marine governance efforts.

Solution

This DUC e creates a public species-traits database, connecting biological traits to ecosystem services via asset-service matrices.

Statistical models then assess how pressures like coastal development or fishing might alter service delivery, informing adaptive and sustainable MPA planning.

Data and monitoring networks used

Environmental data, Particle size distribution (PSD), Biological observation, In-situ observations.

National Centers for Environmental Information
NATIONAL OCEANIC AND ATMOSPHERIC ADMINISTRATION

Copernicus
Europe's eyes on Earth

Ifremer

Expected Outputs

Global carbon flux maps (3D/4D)

Improved carbon export models

Better integration of observation systems

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated

- **Data integration:** Combines existing and sensor-based data to improve carbon flux estimates
- **Gap identification:** Reveals missing data to strengthen climate and ocean models

Useful for

- Climate modelers and marine scientists
- Policy advisors and governance bodies
- mCDR technology developers and marine carbon project stakeholders

Learn more on development and read the publications

Machine Learning for Ocean Colour Seasonal Forecasting

Chlorophyll-a and primary production are key indicators of marine ecosystem health, carbon cycling, and fisheries productivity. This use case **applies machine learning to improve seasonal forecasting** of these variables, supporting more effective monitoring and marine management.

Challenge

Seasonal forecasts are limited by computational complexity and model uncertainty.

Current systems struggle to predict primary production and chlorophyll variability across regions and depths in a resource-efficient manner.

Solution

This DUC applies machine learning to combine satellite ocean colour data with ocean physics forecasts to produce seasonal forecasts.

The approach increases accuracy while reducing computational costs, enabling scalable and accessible predictions.

Data and monitoring networks used

Physical ocean reanalyses and forecasts, biogeochemical data & more.

Expected Outputs

Seasonal forecasts of ocean colour, chlorophyll and primary production

Insights into the global carbon cycle and plankton dynamics, and their response to physical drivers

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated

- **Climate response anticipation:** Forecasts biological changes linked to ocean variability
- **Management support:** Informs fisheries, aquaculture, and ecosystem monitoring strategies
- **What if Scenarios:** Enables low-cost exploration of how physical changes affect ecosystems and and the global carbon cycle

Useful for

- Environmental agencies and research institutions
- Climate modelers and marine scientists
- Ocean governance bodies

Learn more on development and read the publications

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